

Crowdsourcing versus Expert Fact-Checking

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We are facing a huge wave of new content and statements every day. This new data has to be fact-checked in order for people to be able to rely on it, otherwise we just end up with another fake news. It is common practice to use experts for fact-checking, but an alternative might be outsourcing the tasks to crowds (crowdsourcing), which then proceeds to fact-check the respective claims, which has been already researched by La Barbera, et al. (2020).[1] In this paper we are going to reproduce the aforementioned published paper and lay open our strategy, the key findings found and the difficulties we encountered. Furthermore we will compare our conclusions with the ones of the original authors.

Additional Key Words and Phrases: reproduced, crowdsourcing, assessor bias

1 INTRODUCTION

Information spreads super fast nowadays. This is happening due to many factors, e.g. easy communication via internet. Most humans find themselves in a flood of information in which it is hard to keep track of what is a fact and what is barely true or a lie. Fact-checks are often provided by experts, but an alternative is to outsource the fact-checking to a crowd on the internet. For the original paper, the authors collected data from US-based crowd workers and compared it with the results of the fact-checks of experts from PolitiFact. The gathered data is provided by the authors at <https://github.com/KevinRoitero/crowdsourcingTruthfulness>. And at <https://github.com/flohoch/CrowdsourcingTruthfulnessReproduced> our reproduced code is available.

2 STRATEGY

At first we analyzed the original paper and looked for available data. As referenced above, the datasets were available, but the code was not. Thus we tried to reproduce the code and attempted to draw the same conclusions as the authors. Furthermore we thought about the experimental design and applied a few more tests.

2.1 Difficulties

During the reproduction of the work the biggest difficulties were to understand the data set. Nowhere is described which column stands for what. The naming of the column is only helpful in some cases. In addition, it is not described how the factor values of a column are to be understood. For example, one does not know which participants have which gender. Mainly we had to experiment with the graphs to find out which columns represent which values.

3 DATASET DESCRIPTION

We used the two datasets created by La Barbera et al. which consists of 120 statements randomly chosen from the PolitiFact dataset constructed by Wang[2]. Experts fact-check these political claims in the latter dataset on a 6-level scale (e.g. *Lie* or *Mostly True*). The chosen

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subset contains a balanced number of statements of the classes and the political party. The meaning of the dataset attributes can be found in 1

The two datasets contain the results of crowdsourced fact-checks of the 120 statements. Via Amazon Mechanical Turk US-based crowd workers evaluated each 8 of the political claims by labeling the truthfulness in the 6-level scale (S6), which was also used in the PolitiFact dataset, and a 100-level scale (S100). The S100 was entered by a slider with the default value 50. The 8 statements per worker contained 3 statements of Republican speakers, 3 statements of Democratic speakers and 2 gold questions to ensure the quality of the worker.

4 RESULTS

Each dataset consists of 200 crowd workers. In the S6 survey, 108 workers were aligned to the US Democratic Party (Dem) and 92 for the US Republican Party (Rep). In the S100 survey 109 Dem and 91 Rep workers participated. So it can be said, that the participants were balanced across the political spectrum.

Fig. 1. Distribution of scores aggregated by mean: S6. The red line indicates the cumulative distribution of judgments.

4.1 Judgment Distributions

Figure 1 and 2 shows the rating distributions for both the S6 scale and the S100 scale. It seems like that the users have the tendency to use fewer values than available. It also can be seen that the values 0,50 and 100 are way more often used than other values. Figure 3 and 4 shows the outcome in aggregated scores. Values at both ends of the scale seems to be less frequent than other values. These would suggest to use a scale with fewer values.

4.2 Crowd vs. Experts

In figure 5 and 6 the comparison between the crowd workers ratings and the expert judgement can be seen on both the S6 and the

Table 1. Meaning of the attributes of the dataset

Attributes	Meaning
doc_party	Gives information about the political background of the speaker.
rel	The judgement of a political statement by an expert.
gender	The gender is represented by the values 1 and 2. There is no further description, which value which gender represents.
age	The age of the crowd worker. The age is divided in groups.
school	The education of the crowd worker. There is no further description, for the meaning of the possible school values.
income	The income of the crowd worker. There is no further description, for the meaning of the possible income values.
party_in	The party elected by the worker. 1 represents the US Republican Party and 2 the US Democratic Party
ideo	There is no description about the meaning of this attribute
elections	There is no description about the meaning of this attribute
teaparty	There is no description about the meaning of this attribute
positions_in_task	The position of the task in the Amazon Turks survey.
S6_rel	Score given to the statement (just in s6 DataSet)
S100_rel	Score given to the statement (just in s100 DataSet)
justification	justification for score
url	Reference to justification
off_page_count	There is no description about the meaning of this attribute
time	Taken Time for handling the statement

Fig. 2. Distribution of scores aggregated by mean: S100. The red line indicates the cumulative distribution of judgments.

Fig. 4. Comparison of crowd labels with expert ground truth: S100.

Fig. 3. Comparison of crowd labels with expert ground truth: S6.

Fig. 5. Comparison of expert ground truth with crowd labels: S6.

S100 scale. Crowd workers seem to be able to differentiate among

Fig. 6. Comparison of expert ground truth with crowd labels: S100.

different levels because the median values are following the expert judgements. To proof that, we used a t-test to compare the crowd workers score with the expert score. The test showed that except for the combinations **LIE-FALSE**, **FALSE-BARELYTRUE** and **MOSTLYTRUE-TRUE** all combination are significantly different ($p < 0.01$). It seems like that the crowd workers are more gracious than the experts. When the crowd evaluates the truth of the statements for the lowest categories, they tend not to use the lowest value. This can be seen in both scales. It also seems like the the S6 scale is more suitable that S100 scale. The S6 scale seems to match more with the expert judgement than the S100 scale. As we can see in Figure 3 the boxplots are wider for the S100 scale. It also can be seen that the categories in the s100 scale are less separable. This can be observed for the three classes **LIE**, **FALSE** and **BARELY TRUE**.

4.3 Crowd Assessor Bias

Figure 7, 8, 9, 10, 11 and 12 shows how crowd workers evaluated statements based on their political background. We can see that crowd workers with a Rep party background tend to rate higher truthfulness scores to statements. This can especially be seen for the ground truth labels **LIE** and **FALSE**. If we take a look at the statements with a ground truth value **TRUE** from Dem speakers we can see that crowd workers with a Rep party background rate these statement with a lower truthfulness score. We carried out t test to see weather there is a significant difference between the two parties concerning the **TRUE** statements or not. But in fact there is no significant difference as it might look. We can also see that crowd workers tend to give higher scores to **TRUE** statements if they voted for their speaker's party (see Table 2). Finally it can also be said that crowd workers with a Dem party background seems to be more skeptical than crowd workers with a Rep party background.

4.4 Additional Test

As a complement to the work, we asked ourselves some additional questions. For example, whether there is a correlation between the accuracy of the assessment and the time required to guess the statement. In addition, we look at whether there are recognizable differences in the genders.

Fig. 7. Comparison of ground truth with Dem workers (blue) and Rep workers (red): S6. Statements from Rep speakers and Dem speakers.

Fig. 8. Comparison of ground truth with Dem workers (blue) and Rep workers (red): S100. Statements from Rep speakers and Dem speakers.

Fig. 9. Comparison of ground truth with Dem workers (blue) and Rep workers (red): S6. Statements from Dem speakers.

4.4.1 Time Related Correlation. To see the relationship between correct estimation and time, we have created an additional column that contains truth values. A row is called correct if the crowd

Table 2. Mean Crowd Assessor score across party speakers

	Democrat Speaker [S6]	Republican Speaker[S6]	Democrat Speaker [S100]	Republican Speaker[S100]
Democrat Assessor	5.5	4.9	84.1	81.7
Republican Assessor	4.9	5.4	76	82.1

Fig. 10. Comparison of ground truth with Dem workers (blue) and Rep workers (red): S100. Statements from Dem speakers.

Fig. 12. Comparison of ground truth with Dem workers (blue) and Rep workers (red): S100. Statements from Rep speakers.

Fig. 11. Comparison of ground truth with Dem workers (blue) and Rep workers (red): S6. Statements from Rep speakers.

assessor judged the statement the same as the expert. In figure fig:time on the left side you can see that there are no big differences. When performing a t-test, no significant difference can be found. The same is true when the accuracy of the correctness is reduced. That is, if the estimate of the statement is missed by one (for example, Lie instead of False). Even then, no significant differences in time can be found.

4.4.2 Gender Comparison. In Figure 14 we see the distribution of scores from 1-6 on the ground truth. The data set did not contain exact information which gender is which. So both genders are labeled as "1" and "2" without knowing which is male or female. The estimation of gender "2" seems to be hardly different especially for

Fig. 13. Comparison from time to correct estimated statements (left) and nearly correct estimated statements(right)

Fig. 14. crowd assessor scores across expert judgment levels by gender

"Lie", "False" and "Barely True". A t-test comparing crowd assessor scores of gender "2" across expert judgment levels shows that crowd scores are significantly different ($p < 0.01$) across all levels

except for the class combinations **BARELYTRUE - HALFTRUE** and **HALFTRUE - MOSTLYTRUE**. And for the other sex **FALSE - BARELYTRUE**, **HALFTRUE - MOSTLYTRUE** and **HALFTRUE - FALSE**.

5 CONCLUSIONS

In this paper we reproduced the work of La Barbera et al. and can confirm their conclusions. The presented data indicates that crowdsourced judgments can be compared to the ones of experts. Furthermore it is shown that the political background of crowd workers does influence their choice on rating the statements, due to them being more lenient towards statements of the same political

orientation. Although when testing this hypothesis there was no significant difference between the two groups. Finally, crowd workers scored more truthfully when using the 6-level scale instead of the widely ranged 100-level scale.

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